

PHYSICAL AND CHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF BUFFALO MILK SAMPLES AVAILABLE IN UDGIR TOWN LATUR DISTRICT OF MARATHWADA REGION

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(MS Received: 18.05.2023; MS Revised:22.06.2023; MS Accepted:23.06.2023)

MS 3057

(RESEARCH PAPER IN DAIRY SCIENCE,)

Abstract

In order to produce safe and high-quality milk, the first step is to evaluate the quality of raw buffalo milk at the farm level. The world over, milk is referred to as a complete food. Water is most frequently used to dilute milk, which not only lessens its nutritious content but also increases the risk of health issues from contaminated water. The objective of present study is to evaluate Physico-chemical properties of Buffalo Milk samples sold to Udgir town. During present investigation A total of 10 buffalo milk samples were collected from milk vendors in the Udgir area were analysed for milk fat %, milk solids not fat %, TA, Specific gravity, pH and CLR using standardized methods. It was recorded that average fat content was recorded 6.1 ± 0.16 %, SNF was 7.90 ± 0.05 % TS was 14 ± 0.11 , Sp. Gravity was 1.024 ± 0.00 CLR was 25.031 ± 0.23 , pH was 6.4 ± 1.54 respectively. According to statistical analysis, there was a significant difference in the specific gravity, pH, SNF, and TS ($P > 0.05$). In comparison to FSSAI standards, the collected buffalo milk samples were found to have lower specific gravity, SNF, and TS values.

Key Words: Buffalo Milk; Milk Solid Not Fat; CLR; Fat; FSSAI std.; pH Total Solids.; TA

Introduction

Normal pure fresh milk has some standard set of physico-chemical properties and it is also, therefore, called nearly as complete food. The best buffaloes of the world are found in the Indian subcontinent, and India is the leading buffalo country, which produces 96 million tons of milk annually. Buffalo milk (BM) is ranked second after cow milk (CM) in the world as the BM produced is more than 12% of the world's milk production. About 70% of the total BM is produced by India (Khedkar et al., 2016). World milk production has doubled in the last decade, with BM production ranking second after bovine milk. Various compositional and functional properties render the BM eminently suitable for manufacture of dairy products such as ultra-high temperature (UHT) cream, dried ice cream mixes, dairy whiteners, edible casein, and caseinates In India, the milk chain currently moves from the milk producer to the milk collection agent. After that, it gets transported to a milk chilling facility before being sent in bulk to the processing facility, the sales agency, and lastly the consumer. Addition of water, partial skimming or both and adding of preservatives considered one of the important methods for adulteration of raw milk. water Milk producers added to whole milk to increase the volume of milk during summer season, to successfully deal with the demand (Afzal et al., 2011)

According to a 2011 investigation by the Indian Food Safety and Standards Authority, about 70% of samples did not meet the requirements for milk. The investigation discovered that because milk handling and packing lacked sufficient hygiene and sanitation, detergents (used during cleaning operations) weren't thoroughly rinsed and ended up in the milk. In the survey investigation, it was discovered that 8% of samples included detergents that were harmful to human health. Physiochemical properties are important variables for monitoring the milk quality. The best quality of milk for

consumption is usually due to its distinct physical, chemical characteristics. According to Malek dos Reis et al., (2013) milk composition is considered as an important attribute essential for, dairy industries to produce better quality products. Keep in view in mind present study was undertaken to evaluate the quality parameters of buffalo milk sold to Udgir town in the Latur district of Maharashtra state.

Objective: The specific objective is to confirm certain physico-chemical parameters of buffalo milk supplied to udgir town in the Latur district of Maharashtra state as per FSSAI Standard for milk (BM)

Hypothesis: H₀: There is no difference between quality parameters of milk samples sold to udgir town and FSSAI Standard for milk (BM). **H₁:** There is a significant difference between quality parameters of milk samples sold to udgir town and FSSAI Standard for milk (BM). **Materials and Methods:**

Study area: A cross sectional study was done in Udgir urban area. Udgir is a town in the Latur district of the Indian state of Maharashtra during winter season, 2020. Study designs the study involved laboratory tests-based investigation aimed to assess the quality of raw milk samples, supplied to udgir town. A total of L1, L2, L3, L4, L5, L6, L7, L8, L9, L10 (10) samples of raw milk were collected from milk vendors. Highly preferred milk samples coded were selected for the present study. The standard methods were adapted for the analysis of milk quality given by the food science and "FSSAI" and the chemical used were best-graded chemicals. The samples collected were analysed for their physico-chemical study.

Research Design: The study involved a laboratory-based investigation aimed to assess the physico-chemical quality assessment of buffalo milk of raw milk sold to Udgir town.

Fig 1: Research Design

Sample collection: A total of 30 raw buffalo milk samples collected in and around udgir town were collected randomly from local street vendors, dairy shops, dairy farms. The fresh milk samples were collected from the Udgir town. Milk samples of buffalo milk (n = 10), were collected from different dairy farms and vendors from June to December 2019 from different locations of udgir dist. Latur of Maharashtra, India. The area for milk collection was divided into L1 to L10, as the milk is collected at these different areas depending on the type of feed and fodder supplement and grazing conditions. The milk samples were either analysed immediately or stored in a freezer (-20°C) till tested or in the case of delayed analysis. At the time of analysis, samples were brought up to room temperature. Udgir is the second-largest the town and nearby villages rely mainly agriculture and dairying, which serves as a major source of income for the population.

Fig 1: Location Map of the Study Area:

3. Laboratory analysis of milk samples

Physical Analysis: Specific gravity of the milk samples was determined using lactometer.

Determination of Fat Percentage (%): In the present study the Gerber’s method was used for the determination of fat % of milk. (FSSAI ,2012)

Total Solid Percentage (%): Total solid contents of milk were determined by oven dried method. Fresh milk was taken in pre-weighed China dish and evaporated on steam bath. After evaporation milk was dried in an oven at 101°C. Dried milk samples were kept for 1 hour in desiccators in the presence of silica gel and weighed. The process was repeated until constant weight was obtained. Total solids % was calculated by the following formula (AOAC, 1990).

Total solid % = Weight of dried sample x 100/ (Weight of milk sample)

Determination of Solids Not Fat Percentage (%): Solid not fat was determined by the following formula (Harding, 1995)

$$\text{Solid Not Fat (\%)} = \text{Total Solid (\%)} - \text{Fat (\%)} \text{ (FSSAI ,2012)}$$

Determination of Acidity Percentage (%): The acidity of milk can be determined by acid base titration. The milk was taken in a beaker and measured. Few drops of phenolphthalein indicator were added in to the milk. Then NaOH (N/10) was added drop by drop from a burette. Volume of base was recorded on the appearance of pink colour and calculation was made as follows. (FSSAI ,2012)

$$\text{No of ml of N/10 alkali used} \times 0.009$$

$$\text{Acidity \%} = \frac{\text{No of ml of N/10 alkali used} \times 0.009}{\text{Weight of milk in gm}} \times 100$$

Determination of Ph of milk sample: The pH of the samples was determined using pH-meter (Digital pH Meter-111/101, Deep vision instruments).

Statical analysis: The results of the present study presented as mean ± SE (n = 3). The buffalo milk concentration results were statistically analysed by adopting Completely Randomized Design (Amble, 1975), and the data were tested for significant by the one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) at P<0.05.

Results and Discussion

Milk is regarded as a complete food and an excellent source of many nutrients. The major constituents of milk like, fat, total solid, solid not fat, and acidity. Our results show agreement with earlier study reported by Sonwane (2018), Fahmid et al. (2016) were investigated. The composition of milk from different animal species might be affected by a number of factors, such as age, area, breed, feed, and seasonal changes. The quality of buffalo milk samples sold in Udgir town was studied. The result obtained with respective physico-chemical quality of buffalo milk of selected samples in Udgir town represented in table no.1

Table no. 1. Physicochemical assessment of Buffalo milk samples marketed in Udgir town.

Parameters	Mean \pm SE	FSSAI Std. of Buffalo Milk	P-value =0.05	Results
FAT %	6.1 \pm 0.16	6.0	0.143	Non-Sig
SNF %	7.90 \pm 0.05	9.0	0.001	*Sig
TS %	14 \pm 0.11	15.0	0.001	*Sig
ACIDITY %	0.127 \pm 0.006	0.15	0.8	Non-Sig
Sp. Gravity	1.024 \pm 0.00	1.032	0.002	*Sig
pH	6.4 \pm 1.54	6.8	0.00	*Sig
CLR	25.031 \pm 0.23	25	0.8	Non-Sig

(All values of samples shown in table are mean of 3 replications, *Significant P<0.05 level)

Fat Percentage (%): The data revealed that the fat % of milk from locations L1 to L10 average sample were ranged between 6.1 \pm 0.16 %. there no significant difference between the means (p>0.05), the bigger the p-value the stronger it supports H₀. These findings are in agreement with the results of present study for fat % FSSAI Standard of buffalo milk.

Total Solids Percentage (%): When water is removed from milk the remaining constituents are called total solid. Total solid of milk comprises the fat, protein, lactose and minerals. The low values of total solids may be resulted from adulteration of milk with water it also pointed out the extent to which skimming of milk was done. The data revealed that the TS of milk from locations L1 to L10 Total Solid % were the range of 7.90 \pm 0.05, p-value<05. The difference between the averages of samples were big enough to be statistically significant. The smaller the p-value the stronger it supports H₁ Statistically the mean percentages of TS of milk were found significantly different. The TS % of pure milk was 15.00% and in accordance with FSSAI std value. The TS % of milk samples were found lower when compared with the T.S % of pure milk. The concentration of total solids in buffalo milk was found lower than that of FSSAI Standard of buffalo milk. These results do not agree to confirm FSSAI standards (not less than 15%) The variation in TS content might be due to quality and quantity of the feed, stage of lactation, genetical variation our results show agreement with earlier study reported by Fahmid et al., (2016) and Afzal et al., (2011).

Solid Not Fat Percentage (%): The data showed that there were significant differences in SNF% of milk between locations L1 and L10, with a range of 7.90 \pm 0.05 and a p-value =05. Pure milk had an SNF% of 9%, which was within normal limits. When compared to the SNF% for pure milk, the overall SNF% of milk samples were found to be partially lower. The lower values of SNF may be due to extraction of milk fat our results show agreement with earlier study reported by Fahmid et al. (2016). Given that the SNF concentration only decreases with the addition of water and is unaffected by partial skimming, the lower SNF content could be mostly due to adulteration by water addition watering and debasement of milk. (Harding, 1995). All of the constituents of milk, except water and fat, are represented by the solid form of the milk. The milk fat separation or dilution of water can be responsible for the low SNF readings. SNF and density were not according to required FSSAI standard. These results obtained Mean SNF content of different locations are below the FSSAI prescribed (not less than 9%).

Acidity Percentage (%): The information showed that milk from locations L1 through L10 had a specific gravity of Milk's acidity percentage serves as an indicator for its freshness. According to Popescu and Angel (2009), acidity levels in high-grade milk must be less than or equal to 0.14%. The data revealed that milk from locations L1 through L10 had an average acidity of 0.10%. Similar results were found in a study on the quality of raw milk supplied to organized milk collection enters of a private dairy plant in the Nanded district of Maharashtra state (Sonwane, 2018). The average sample's lactic acid percentage ranged between 0.127 and 0.006 and was

found to be non-significantly different (P>0.05). The bigger the p-value the stronger it supports H₀. High values of acidity than normally indicate the poor quality of milk regarding its freshness. Titratable acidity was found to decrease with increasing time as observed by Musallam et al. (2017), while acidity values close to normally indicate the better quality of milk regarding freshness.

CLR of milk samples: Values of CLR of milk were obtained from location L1 to L10 at a temperature of 21° C; the average sample's density CLR ranged between 25.031 and 0.23; this value was found to be non-significantly different (P>0.05); the higher the p-value, the more strongly H₀ is supported. These results are consistent with the buffalo milk FSSAI standard.

Specific gravity of milk samples: The data showed that the specific gravities of milk samples from location L1 to L10 were found to be substantially different, with a p-value =0.05 (1.024 \pm 0.00). Pure milk has a specific gravity of 1.032, which is within the typical range. When compared to the specific gravity of pure milk standard, the specific gravity of milk samples was revealed to be somewhat lower our results show agreement with earlier study reported by Fahmid et al. (2016), Padghan et al., (2008); Braun and Preuss, (2008). Lower results showed that milk had been diluted with water and that skimming had been done. These results do not match those of the current study for SNF% with FSSAI Standard of buffalo milk.

pH of milk samples: The findings revealed that milk from locations L1 through L10 had a mean% of pH The composition of pH varies from species to species, however in the current investigation, the pH of the average sample was between 6.4 \pm 1.54 p-value=05; the smaller the p-value, the more strongly it supports H₁ A significant variation in pH between the sample and the FSSAI standard value was found by statistical analysis. Lower pH levels in milk are the best indicators of udder health as well as of dairy cows' overall good health. Similar findings were made by Hashmi and Saleem (2015), milk samples taken from buffaloes over various seasons and concluded that winter has the highest pH (6.55 0.13). The pH of buffalo milk ranges from 6.57 to 6.84 and is not influenced by month, lactation number, or season of calving, but correlated with solid-not-fat and lactose contents Minieri et al., (1965).

Conclusion: In conclusion, this investigation has demonstrated, based on the data acquired, that the average specific gravity, SNF, and TS of the milk samples were lower than the FSSAI standards prescribed other all parameters of the tested Buffalo milk samples were within the recommended nutritional levels. These findings may be helpful for the concerned governmental parties to monitor the quality of the milk. Drinking milk of high quality may have positive effects on human health. This study has shown that a quality control system is necessary to ensure that milk of the highest quality is sold and to educate regular household consumers about the milk quality in their area.

Acknowledgment

Author gratefully acknowledges the efforts taken by Dr. S.N. Landge, head of the Department of Dairy Science MUM, Udgir his kind support and able guidance for carry out the entire investigation.

Conflict Of Interest: There is no conflict of interest.

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